

Recent Progress in Synthetic Dyes

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The second edition of the Colour Index, published in 1956-58 by the Society of Dyers and Colourists, Manchester, and the American Association of Textile Chemists and Colorists, lists 4702 dyes and allied products, classified both according to their usage and their chemical constitution. The dyes in the former classification are more numerous, because there are many commercial dyes, the structures of which have not been disclosed. In fact, there are very few dyes indeed for which the constitution is given in the new Colour Index and not in a 1952 publication^{1,2} in which it was possible to include the structures of numerous commercial dyes because of the information on the German dyestuff industry which became available after the second world war in BIOS and FIAT reports. For reasons which are not easy to understand, dye manufacturers, unlike the manufacturers of synthetic drugs, are reluctant to reveal the chemical constitution of their products. Nevertheless, it is clear from patents and from publications in which broad structural features are indicated in connection with dyeing properties that there has been no slackening of the search for new synthetic dyes. Comprehensive accounts of progress year by year in the chemistry, technology, and application of colouring matters appear in Reports on the Progress of Applied Chemistry and Review of Textile Progress; and only a few of the developments during the last ten years, chosen somewhat arbitrarily, are outlined in this brief survey.

Azo Dyes

An important addition to the literature of dyestuff chemistry is a book by Zollinger³, who in recent years has materially advanced our knowledge of the diazonium coupling reaction by studying the kinetic isotope (deuterium) effects.

The application of mordant azo dyes was greatly facilitated by the production of water-soluble dyes containing the metal (usually chromium) in co-ordination (Neolan dyes, Ciba; Palatine Fast dyes, I. G.). These were of the type (I) in which the complex contained one atom of chromium and one molecule of the azo dye. The dyeing process had one disadvantage that it involved the use of relatively high concentrations of sulphuric acid.

(I)

(II)

The I. G. first marketed neutral-dyeing metal-dye complexes, such as the blue chromium complex of (II), in which the azo dye contained one or more sulphamyl instead of sulphonic groups. Several of the Perlon Fast dyes, special dyes for synthetic polyamide fibres, were of this type¹. The water-solubility, however, was unsatisfactory. The Geigy Co. then made the discovery that a 2:1 complex of dye and chromium of the type (III), described by Drew and Fairbairn in 1939, fulfilled the requirements for neutral dyeing; the complex (III) is a monobasic acid, which forms a monosodium salt, and the water-solubility is increased to meet the needs for practical dyeing by the introduction of $-\text{SO}_2\text{Me}$ and similar groups⁴. Such dyes are now offered by all the leading dye manufacturers, and an example³ is Irgalan Grey BL (IV).

Japanese and Russian workers are investigating the relation between the constitution of azo dyes and their absorption spectra, dyeing, and fastness properties. In a series of interesting papers B. I. Stepanov has shown that chlorine in *o*-chloro-*o'*-hydroxyazo compounds or in 8-chloro-2'-hydroxyazonaphthalenes can be replaced by an alkoxy or phenoxy group by heating the copper complex (prepared separately or *in situ*) with sodium alkoxide or phenoxide in toluene.

The general method for determining the structure of azo dyes is to reduce them under neutral, acid, or alkaline conditions and identify the arylamines and their sulphonic acids thus obtained. The isolation of arylamine sulphonic acids from aqueous solution and their characterization have been facilitated by chromatographic methods. Conversion of the arylamines, phenols, and their sulphonic acids to the coloured 2,4-dinitrophenyl derivatives, or into condensation products with cyanuric chloride, which are further treated with dimethylamine, offers advantages and is under investigation⁵.

Reactive Dyes for Cellulose

The use of cyanuric chloride for linking two or three molecules of the same or different dyes containing free amino groups has been the subject of numerous patents, mainly of the Ciba Co., and the first account of the preparation and properties of the cyanurated dyes was given by Fierz-David and Matter in 1937. A recent development, which represents a landmark in the history of synthetic dyes, is the application of dyes of the type (V),

which are capable of entering into stable chemical combination with cellulose in presence of alkali, unlike the known dyes for cellulose fibres which attach themselves to the cellulose macromolecule by hydrogen bonding and/or van der Waals' forces. The Procion (I.C.I.) and Cibacron (Ciba) are such "reactive" dyes. The structures of Procion and Cibacron dyes are illustrated by (V), (VI) (VII), (VIII) and (IX).

The yellow to red dyes are monoazo; the blues are derivatives of 1-amino-4-anilino-anthraquinone-2-sulphonic acid or phthalocyanine; and the greens are mixtures or condensation products of blue and yellow dyes. Lack of substantivity is regarded as an advantage, because any dye, substantively adsorbed but not chemically combined with the fibre, will lead to poor wash fastness. Thus the dyes are constituted like typical acid dyes and do not possess the structural features characteristic of direct cotton dyes. The new Colour Index lists only three azo dyes derived from cyanuric chloride (Colour Index 34040; 34045; 28500); the first two (Coprantine Green G and Chlorantine Fast Green BLL) contain no

chlorine attached to the triazine ring and are therefore unreactive dyes; the last (Chlorantine Fast Blue 8G) has one chlorine free, but is not applied as a reactive dye. The second and third chlorine atoms in the triazine ring react with some of the primary alcoholic groups in cellulose. The dichlorotriazines, such as (V), to which type most of the Procions (other than the Procion H brand) belong, react with cellulose in presence of sodium carbonate at room temperature or by warming; a secondary reaction, which can take place with the dichlorotriazines, is cross-linking of the cellulose chains, rendering the dyed fibre insoluble in cuprammonium hydroxide solution⁶. The monochlorotriazines, such as (VII), representing the Procion H and Cibacron dyes, require a higher temperature as well as a stronger base for interaction with cellulose; their greater stability also results in less decomposition on storage.

Wegmann has studied the relation between constitution and dyeing properties of the reactive dyes derived from cyanuric chloride⁷. The structures of some of the Cibacron dyes have been determined by Panchartek *et al*⁸. Two examples are Cibacron Brilliant Yellow 3G (Procion Brilliant Yellow H5GS; X) and Cibacron Brilliant Blue BR (VIII in which one chlorine is replaced by metanilic acid). Bao-Chi-Min has synthesized a series of such dyes and examined their fastness properties⁹.

The success of the Procion and Cibacron dyes has led to a search for dyes containing reactive halogen in other heterocyclic rings such as pyrimidine and phthalazine or in simpler groups such as sulphonyl fluoride. Thus the dye (XI), fixed on the cotton fibre with acid-binding agents, gives greenish yellow shades which are fast to light and washing, Krazer and Zollinger¹⁰ have shown that the dyed fibre is a sulphonic ester, in which the dye is replaced by iodine on treatment with sodium iodide in acetone. This reaction is specific for dyes containing SO₂F groups; and other methods for characterizing the dye-fibre bond, such as microbiological degradation, isotope technique and solubility tests, have been discussed by Zollinger.

In the Remazol dyes of B.A.S.F., which also combine with cellulose by covalent bonds, the interaction depends on a different mechanism. The dyes are of the general type D-SO₂CH₂CH₂OSO₂Na, in which D is a dye molecule¹¹. When a Remazol is applied to cotton or viscose by a printing process or by dyeing at 60° in presence of sodium carbonate, it decomposes to a vinyl sulphone (D-SO₂-CH=CH₂), which then combines with cellulose to form compounds of the type D-SO₂-CH₂CH₂-O-Ce. The reactivity of the Remazols appears to lie between the monochloro- and dichlorotriazines. The Remazols now available are mainly suitable for printing. Dyes containing the group -NHCOCH₂CH₂Cl probably react via the acrylamide -NHCOCH=CH₂. Isoyanate and other groups capable of interaction with alcoholic hydroxyl groups are potentially useful in the synthesis of reactive dyes, but the general problems are (a) their application to fibres under practical dye-

ing conditions, keeping the competitive reaction with water or aqueous alkali to a minimum, and (b) the removal of dye not combined with cellulose by a simple washing treatment which does not break the ester-type cellulose-dye bond.

The Procion and other 'reactive' dyes are by no means free from technical disadvantages such as instability on prolonged storage and loss of colour in the dyebath for the obvious reason that the reactive chlorine atoms can combine with water as well as with the hydroxyl groups of cellulose. These doubtless have great possibilities in dyeing and printing cellulose fibres, but there is no reason to believe that they threaten in any way the future of the well established azoic and vat dyes, which have much higher fastness to washing.

Azoic Dyes

Naphtol AS-FGGR, a phthalocyanine derivative, is mentioned later. The structures of eight Naphtols, not mentioned in the 'Chemistry of Synthetic Dyes', are disclosed in the new 'Colour Index'. Five of them are simple derivatives of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, described in old patents or publications¹²; AS-AN is the *p*-nitroanilide, AS-MCA the *m*-chloroanilide, AS-AM the *m*-4-xylylide, AS-KB the 2-methyl-5-chloroanilide, and AS-BM the *o*-toluidide. Naphtol AS-BI is the *o*-aniside of 6-bromo-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid¹³. The yellow-producing Naphtols AS-IRG and AS-IFG are 4-chloro-2,5-dimethoxyacetanilide and benzoylacet-4-benzamido-2,5-dimethoxyanilide; they are suitable for printing, but do not possess adequate substantivity for use in dyeing¹⁴.

Only one new Fast Base (diazotizing component) is mentioned in the new Colour Index: Fast Red Base PDC, which is the *n*-butyl amide of 3-amino-4-methoxybenzenesulphonic acid.

An interesting reaction of *o*-hydroxybenzamides, useful for the hydrolysis of Naphtols and identification of the acid and amine components, is their behaviour towards cyanuric chloride and 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene, both of which attack the amide nitrogen and not the phenolic hydroxyl group¹⁵. The reaction appears to proceed by a direct displacement of the halogen by the amide nitrogen involving intramolecular nucleophilic catalysis by the phenoxide oxygen; but a Smiles rearrangement is not completely excluded. The *N*-dinitrophenyl derivatives are stable to boiling hydrochloric acid, but are hydrolysed easily by aqueous sodium carbonate or hydroxide. Thus Naphtol AS-RS and AS-KN have been shown to be the 4-chloro-2-methoxy-5-methylanilide (XII) of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid and the α -naphthylamide (XIII) of 3-hydroxydibenzofuran-2-carboxylic acid respectively.

Mild alkaline hydrolysis of the *N*-dinitrophenyl derivative of a Naphthol leads readily to the brightly coloured and easily crystallizable dinitrodiphenylamine-corresponding to the amine component; the yield of the acid component of the Naphthol is variable, and better yields of the acid are obtained by hydrolysis of the *N*-cyanuryl derivative (XIV). When (XIV) is treated with dimethylamine, the two reactive chlorine atoms are replaced and the product (XV) then undergoes very smooth hydrolysis to the acid and the triazine derivative (XVI). Thus it has been shown that the constitution of Naphtol AS-KG is (XVII)⁵.

Dinitrochlorobenzene attacks the reactive methylene group in acetoacetanilide on heating an ethanolic solution containing a molar proportion of sodium hydroxide; under these conditions the acetyl group is split off and the product is 2,4-dinitrophenyl-acetanilide (XVIII). Similarly Naphtol AS-IRG (XIX) yields (XX)⁵.

The Neocotone dyes of Ciba have been withdrawn from the commercial range and do not find a place in the new Colour Index; but their chemical constitution is of interest. They have been stated in the literature to be of the type (XXI), prepared by condensing a pre-formed azoic dye (XXII) with *m*-sulphobenzoyl chloride¹⁶, but this needs confirma-

tion since the hydroxyl group in 1-benzeneazo-2-hydroxy-3-naphthanilide (XXII) is likely to be unreactive.

(XXI)

(XXII)

Vat Dyes

Patent activity on indigoids has almost ceased; in the anthraquinone field there are only minor structural variations of the established types. This area, however, offers numerous problems for research on constitution, reaction mechanism, steric effects, light absorption, and photochemical activity in the degradation of cellulose. Considering the technical importance of the vat dyes, fundamental work on these problems has been very limited¹⁷.

Vat dyes not derived from anthraquinone or benzanthrone can be prepared from 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone¹⁸ and some dyes of this type appear to have technical possibilities^{19,20}. Examples are the bright orange dye (XXIII) and the red-brown to violet dyes (XXIV) in which the ring system carries nitro, amino, and other substituents.

(XXIII)

(XXIV)

Phthalocyanines

Because of the brightness and stability of the phthalocyanine pigments, attempts have been made for many years to apply them to textiles. Partly sulphonated cobalt phthalocyanine behaves as a vat dye and has been marketed (Indanthrene Brilliant Blue 4G), but the chlorine fastness is poor. The mechanism of the reduction and re-oxidation of cobalt

phthalocyanine has not yet been elucidated. When phthalocyanines are treated in methanol with oxidizing agents such as butyl hypochlorite, chlorine, bromine or dibenzoyl peroxide, the red-brown products are soluble in solvents such as ethylene glycol monomethyl ether, and the solutions may be used for padding cotton, the original phthalocyanine being regenerated by treatment with a reducing agent such as sodium bisulphite or hydrosulphite. Solvent-soluble products of copper and nickel phthalocyanines resulting from reversible oxidation can also be obtained by treating metal-free phthalocyanines with a halogen in an alcoholic solution of a salt of copper or nickel²¹.

By suitable reactions on phthalonitrile or phthalimide or their derivatives, iso-indolenines can be isolated as intermediates in phthalocyanine synthesis; iso-indolenines such as (XXV), (XXVI) and (XXVII; R=H or Ph) (Phthalogens, Bayer) can be printed on textile fabrics together with a copper salt, and under mild conditions of heating or steaming the metal phthalocyanine is formed on the fibre as a brilliant pigment with excellent fastness properties^{22,23}.

The action of dimercaptomaleic acid diinitrile on ethylene dihalogenides yields 1,2-dicyano-3,6-dithiacyclohexene (XXVIII), which is useful for the preparation of pure and mixed phthalocyanines, thus expanding the colour scale of the phthalocyanines to violet, dark blue and black²⁴.

A clear yellowish green azoic dye has now become available, although the Naphthol has the disadvantage that it has no affinity for cellulose fibres and can only be applied to cotton by padding or Rapidogen printing. Fast green shades are produced from Naphthol AS-FGGR, which is copper phthalocyanine to which four pyrazolone rings have been linked by chromophore-insulating groups (such as CONH)²⁵.

Pigments

The triphenyldioxazine (XXIX) is a reddish violet pigment with high light-fastness and tinctorial value, disclosed in a patent some years ago, but it found little use commercially because of its very severe flocculation in paint systems. An important advance is the application of this pigment (or its chloro or bromo derivative) after treating it with the aluminium salt of the pigment substituted by carboxyl or sulphonic groups; the treated pigments are not altered tinctorially, but exhibit excellent resistance to flocculation in paint systems²⁵.

Quinacridones (XXX; 5, 14-7, 12-tetrahydro-5, 12-diazapentacene-7, 14-dione), carrying halogen, alkyl or alkoxy substituents, are brilliant orange to violet pigments of high fastness and durability. The linear quinacridones can be obtained in three crystal phases, α , β , and γ with distinctive shade and pigment properties.

Mechanism of Dyeing Cellulose

Theories of dyeing, so far at least as cellulose fibres are concerned, keep going round in a circle²⁷. The tendency of a fibre to adsorb a dye from aqueous solution and to retain it, which is the basis of normal dyeing processes, is sometimes termed "substantivity." In his book²⁸ on the physical chemistry of dyeing Vickerstaff has ably expounded the thermodynamic approach to dyeing, defining the affinity of a dye for a fibre as the difference in the standard chemical potential of the dye in the fibre phase and the solution phase. He therefore measures substantivity in terms of the change in free energy accompanying the adsorption of the dye, and he has developed equations for evaluating substantivity. Wegmann²⁹ rejects this concept of substantivity; Wirz and Zollinger³⁰ in their recent work on the substantivity of polyene dicarboxylic acids and quaternary ammonium salts derived from benzidine have limited themselves to the determination of "relative substantivity" as the ratio of dye on the fibre to dye in solution after equilibrium has been attained. The greater the shift in equilibrium in favour of the adsorbed dye, the greater the degree of substantivity. Their conclusion that the substantivity of these compounds is mainly or exclusively due to van der Waals forces is valid, but as Zollinger himself has stated³¹ these experiments do not prove that no hydrogen bonding to cellulose takes place in direct dyes³². It has to be recognized that no simple generalization can cover all dyeing mechanisms. Dyeing processes depend on the operation of one or more of three forces: van der Waals forces (electronic dispersion forces), hydrogen bonds, and electrostatic forces. If we consider a dye whose structure permits hydrogen bonding as well as van der Waals and coulombic attractions, no methods are yet available by which these can be separately determined.

Another aspect of the substantivity of dyes to cellulose, which needs much more investigation and about which some misconceptions persist, is the need for planarity and for the spacing of groups in a dye molecule at certain distances to enable hydrogen bonding to take place. Because of the large number of hydroxyl groups in cellulose and the flexibility of the cellulose chain, it is necessary to repeat the point made elsewhere that all substantive dyes need not be "long, linear and planar molecules" as stated so frequently. Considerable deviations in both these factors of planarity and spacing of hydrogen-bonding groups are permissible, and several examples of dyes illustrating this view have been cited³³. The possibilities of hydrogen bonding and the complexity of the whole problem of cellulose-dye interaction are shown by the formula of a simple and well-known direct cotton dye, Diamine Sky Blue FF.

Diamine Sky Blue FF

The Dyestuff Industry in India

In a volume dedicated to the memory of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray, the pioneer of the Indian chemical industry, it is appropriate to record the rapid expansion of the dyestuff industry in India. The list of dye and pigment manufacturers in the new Colour Index includes several Indian firms. Although the industry is at present largely based on imported intermediates, there is reason to hope that all the basic intermediates will be manufactured and that a self-contained industry, which will fully meet our requirements of dyes and related organic chemicals, will be established in the course of the next few years.

One aspect of the manufacture of organic intermediates and dyes on which the attention of Indian manufacturers, especially those operating on a small scale and with inadequate resources, needs to be focussed is the increasing consciousness in other countries of chemical carcinogenesis and other health hazards. The use of β -naphthylamine, the most active carcinogen among dye intermediates, is being eliminated, and attempts are being made to synthesize β -naphthylamine derivatives, such as Naphtol AS-SW and Indanthrene Red RK, from 2-naphthylamine-1-sulphonic acid (Tobias acid)²⁴ or by other routes. Arsenic pentoxide is used in halogenations and aminations but procedures by which it can be avoided are being sought. Health hazards in handling chemicals are considerably increased under hot and humid conditions. Benzanthrone, for instance, appears to present no special problem elsewhere, but photochemical toxicity has been observed in India. Stringent precautions should be enforced in dyestuff factories, and a programme of research on the physiological action of the largely used organic intermediates under Indian conditions should be undertaken.

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